

COAGULOPATHY AND THROMBOSIS IN THE CONSUMPTION OF CONTRACEPTIVES**Maximenco Iulian,***Student at "Nicolae Testemițanu" State University of Medicine and Pharmacy
Saint Stephen the Great Boulevard 165, Chisinau 2004, Moldova***Ambros Ala***PhD, university lector**Department of Biochemistry and Clinical Biochemistry
Nicolae Testemițanu Street 27, Chisinau, Moldova***Abstract**

Hormonal contraceptives exert prothrombotic effects, related to estrogen (intensification of gene expression of coagulation factors II, VII, VIII, X, XII, fibrinogen, von Willebrand factor, heparanase, TAFI, induction of PCa resistance, decrease in expression of antithrombin, factor V, activation inflammation, vasodilatation in non-optimal conditions) as well as antithrombotic effects (activation of PS and TFPI, increase in PAI-1 gene expression and decrease in T-PA gene expression). Progestins activate heparanase, and induce vasodilation. Therefore, contraceptives have diametrically opposite effects, and the pro- or anti-thrombotic result largely depends on the pre-existing coagulant background. Different methods of hormonal contraception have distinct thrombotic risks. The thrombotic effect of estrogen is dose-dependent, diminishing at low doses. But even at doses of 10 µg, the prothrombotic effect persists. There is a difference between the types of estrogens. Thus, the use of estradiol valerate and estradiol decreases the thrombotic risk compared to ethinyl estradiol.

Keywords: hormonal contraception, mechanism of coagulopathy, methods of contraception, coagulation factors, heparanase.

Introduction

Hormonal contraceptives are widely used and effective if used correctly. Since the 1960s, HC have become widespread, and it is now estimated that more than 150 million women use them globally. Deep vein thrombosis and pulmonary embolism, collectively called venous thromboembolism (VTE), occur at an annual rate of 5 cases per 10,000 women of reproductive age, representing approximately 67,000 annual cases of VTE in the European Union, where there are approx. 134 million women between the ages of 15 and 54 [2]. The results of epidemiological studies on the risk of VTE associated with hormonal contraceptives (CH) have varied, with some showing no difference in risk between CH (prospective active surveillance studies) while others showing an increased risk (observational studies or databases) [10]. The aim of the research is the elucidation of the biochemical processes of normal hemostasis, with the determination of the mechanisms by which hormonal contraceptives induce coagulopathies, the description of the types of hormonal contraceptives and their distinct action on coagulation.

Materials and methods

The given work represents a bibliographic study based on current scientific literature to determine the mechanisms that lead to coagulation disorders in the consumption of contraceptives.

Articles, books, websites and scientific publications from 175 bibliographic sources based on data from: PubMed, Medscape, National Library of Medicine, Frontiers, BMJ, WHO, international guidelines and published national and international clinical protocols were used. The period of their publication being primarily 2013-2023.

Results

The coagulation mechanisms of HC are: estrogen administered orally will pass through the liver, inducing changes in blood coagulation and anticoagulant proteins: it increases the synthesis of coagulation factors II, VII, VIII, X, XII, fibrinogen, protein C, protein S, TFPI and thrombin-activatable fibrinolysis inhibitor (TAFI) and decreases the synthesis of others: factor V and antithrombin (AT) [7,11]. It acts on fibrinolysis by increasing the level of tissue plasminogen activator and decreasing the level of PAI-1, but due to TAFI the overall effect is antifibrinolytic. The other mechanisms are: proinflammatory effect at low doses, grow of heparanase activity (increase TF and decrease TFPI), vasodilatory effect of estrogen (compromised veins of the lower limbs) [8,12].

Progestins have also been shown to have a procoagulant effect, even in the absence of estrogen. The first mechanism is also caused by increased heparanase activity. It does this through estrogen receptors. Progestins of the 3rd and 4th generation, which demonstrate more intense procoagulant effects, have been shown to influence heparanase the most. The second mechanism is vasodilatation [9,12].

The correlation of HC methods and the intensity of the procoagulant effect, argued on the basis of clinical studies is represented in table 1. According to clinical studies, COCs of the 1st, 3rd, 4th generation, the vaginal ring and the transdermal patch have the greatest risk. The 2nd generation COC, Norgestimate (GEN 3 COC), medroxyprogesterone injection have an average risk. The intrauterine device, implant, progestin pills and emergency contraception have the lowest risk. The dose difference of ethinylestradiol demonstrates a dose-dependent procoagulant effect. Increasing the dose increases the risk. Among the different types of estrogens, estradiol valerate (E2) and estradiol (E4) have been shown to be less procoagulant and safer.

Table 1.

Correlation between HC method and procoagulant effect

Method of HC	Dose EE	Type of progestine	RR, OR, estimate risk	References
1. OC				
I gen	30-40 µg	Ciproteron	OR 4,0*	Stegeman et al.
II gen	30-40 µg	LNG	OR 2,38*/RR 1,63*	LaVasseur et al. Weill et al.
III gen	30-40 µg	Desogestrol	OR 4,28 *	LaVasseur et al.
	20-30 µg	Desogestrol	RR 2,16 **	Weill et al.
	30-40 µg	Gestoden	OR 3,64*	LaVasseur et al.
	20-30 µg	Gestoden	RR 2,16*	Weill et al.
	30-40 µg	Norgestimate	OR 2,53*	LaVasseur et al.
IV gen	30-40 µg	Drosperinonă	OR 4,0*	Stegeman et al.
	30-40 µg	Drosperinonă	RR 1,40**	Oedingen et al.
2. Vaginal ring	13-15 µg/zi	Etonogestrel	RR 1,90** RR 6,5*	Lidegaard et al.
3. Transdermal patch	30 µg/zi	LNG	OR 2,0***	Fleischer et al./ Dore et al.
			RR 7,9*	Lidegaard et al.
4. Injection	-	Depo medroxyprogesteron	OR 2,2* RR 3,6*	Bergendal et al. Hylckama et al.
5. Emergency contraception	#	#	#	
6. Progestin pills	-	Noretindrona Drospirenona	OR 1,03*	Tepper et al.
7. IUD	-	LNG	OR 1,03*	Tepper et al.
8. Implant	-	LNG	OR 1,03*	Tepper et al.
The difference between different doses of EE				
	20 µg 30-40 µg	-	RR 0,75**** RR 1****	Weill et al. Weill et al.
The difference between different types of estrogens				
EE și E2 EE și E4	- -	- -	6,9/10.000 9,9/10.000	Grandi et al.

Note: reference variable

* not exposed/ not ill lipsa de expunere/lipsa bolii

** OC with LNG with the same dose of EE

*** OC with Norgestimate 30-40 µg

**** OC with the same type of progestine and 30-40 µg EE

References

1. Bergendal Annica et al. "Association of Venous Thromboembolism With Hormonal Contraception and Thrombophilic Genotypes." *Obstetrics & Gynecology* vol. 124 no. 3 Ovid Technologies (Wolters Kluwer Health) Sept. 2014 pp. 600–09. Crossref <https://doi.org/10.1097/aog.0000000000000411>.

2. Blondon M. Update on Oral Contraception and Venous Thromboembolism. În: "Educational Updates in Hematology Book: 25th Congress of the European Hematology Association Virtual Edition 2020." *HemaSphere* vol. 4 Ovid Technologies (Wolters Kluwer Health) June 2020 pp 156-158. Crossref <https://doi.org/10.1097/hs9.0000000000000444>.

3. Dore David D. et al. "Extended Case-control Study Results on Thromboembolic Outcomes Among Transdermal Contraceptive Users." *Contraception* vol.

81 no. 5 Elsevier BV May 2010 pp. 408–13. Crossref <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.contraception.2009.12.009>.

4. Fleischer K. et al. "Effects of the Contraceptive Patch the Vaginal Ring and an Oral Contraceptive on APC Resistance and SHBG: A Cross-over Study." *Thrombosis Research* vol. 123 no. 3 Elsevier BV Jan. 2009 pp. 429–35. Crossref <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.thromres.2008.04.022>.

5. Grandi Giovanni et al. "Confirmation of the Safety of Combined Oral Contraceptives Containing Oestradiol on the Risk of Venous Thromboembolism." *The European Journal of Contraception & Reproductive Health Care* vol. 27 no. 2 Informa UK Limited Feb. 2022 pp. 83–84. Crossref <https://doi.org/10.1080/13625187.2022.2029397>.

6. Hylckama Vlieg Astrid van et al. "The Risk of Deep Venous Thrombosis Associated With Injectable Depot–Medroxyprogesterone Acetate Contraceptives

or a Levonorgestrel Intrauterine Device.” *Arteriosclerosis Thrombosis and Vascular Biology* vol. 30 no. 11 Ovid Technologies (Wolters Kluwer Health) Nov. 2010 pp. 2297–300. Crossref <https://doi.org/10.1161/atvbaha.110.211482>.

7. LaVasseur Corinne et al. “Hormonal Therapies and Venous Thrombosis: Considerations for Prevention and Management.” *Research and Practice in Thrombosis and Haemostasis* vol. 6 no. 6 Elsevier BV Aug. 2022 p. e12763. Crossref <https://doi.org/10.1002/rth2.12763>.

8. Lidegaard O. et al. “Venous Thrombosis in Users of Non-oral Hormonal Contraception: Follow-up Study Denmark 2001-10.” *BMJ* vol. 344 no. may10 3 *BMJ* May 2012 pp. e2990–e2990. Crossref <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.e2990>.

9. Oedingen Carina et al. “Systematic Review and Meta-analysis of the Association of Combined Oral Contraceptives on the Risk of Venous Thromboembolism: The Role of the Progestogen Type and Estrogen Dose.” *Thrombosis Research* vol. 165 Elsevier BV May 2018 pp. 68–78. Crossref <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.thromres.2018.03.005>.

10. Sitruk-Ware Regine. “Hormonal Contraception and Thrombosis.” *Fertility and Sterility* vol. 106 no. 6 Elsevier BV Nov. 2016 pp. 1289–94. Crossref <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fertnstert.2016.08.039>.

11. Stegeman B. H. et al. “Different Combined Oral Contraceptives and the Risk of Venous Thrombosis: Systematic Review and Network Meta-analysis.” *BMJ* vol. 347 no. sep12 1 *BMJ* Sept. 2013 pp. f5298–f5298. Crossref <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.f5298>.

12. Tepper Naomi K. et al. “Progestin-only Contraception and Thromboembolism: A Systematic Review.” *Contraception* vol. 94 no. 6 Elsevier BV Dec. 2016 pp. 678–700. Crossref <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.contraception.2016.04.014>.

13. Weill Alain et al. “Low Dose Oestrogen Combined Oral Contraception and Risk of Pulmonary Embolism Stroke and Myocardial Infarction in Five Million French Women: Cohort Study.” *BMJ* *BMJ* May 2016 p. i2002. Crossref <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.i2002>. [Original source: <https://studycrumb.com/alphabetizer>]